

**Studies in Copper(II) Chelates. Part IX.
Mixed Chelates with Tridentate Dibasic
(ONS) Schiff Bases and α,α' -Dipyridyl
(or *o*-Phenanthroline)**

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A previous report¹ has described our interest in the mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) containing tridentate hydrozone Schiff bases (donor set ONO) and a bidentate dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline). Copper(II) complexes of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone Schiff base (LH₂) were reported by Muto². We describe herein mixed chelates of copper(II) with some thiolato type Schiff bases (donor set ONS) and dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline). While this study was progressing Ablov *et al*³ reported the synthesis of two of the compounds reported in this note, namely, [Cu(dipy)(L)]2H₂O and [Cu(*o*-phen)(L)]H₂O without elucidating the structure of the mixed chelates.

Experimental

5-chlorosalicylaldehyde was prepared by standard method⁴. Thiosemicarbazide, salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde were of reagent grade quality. The Schiff bases were obtained by refluxing equimolar amount of thiosemicarbazide and the appropriate aldehyde in ethanol for one to two hours on a steam bath.

General Preparative Procedure

Copper(II) acetate dihydrate (0.001 mole in 20 ml ethanol) and dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) (0.0012 mole in 5 ml ethanol) were mixed and warmed on a water bath for a minute when a clear deep blue solution was obtained. This solution was then added to the yellow solution of the Schiff bases (0.001 mole in 30 ml ethanol) when the colour of the solution changed to dark brown. Within a few minutes a product began to separate. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr, cooled to room temperature and filtered. A brown, green or black crystalline product was thus obtained, which was washed with alcohol and dried in air.

In the case of the ligand derived from thiosemicarbazide and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (LH₂; Ia X = 5,6 benzo) which is sparingly soluble, the appropriate amount (0.001 mole) was dissolved in 70 ml ethanol. After refluxing the volume was reduced and the product handled as described above.

Analysis: Sulphur was determined as sulphate⁵ after oxidation with sodium peroxide and sodium carbonate. Copper was estimated iodometrically by standard procedure after the complex has been ignited to copper oxide being followed by dissolution

in a mixture of sulphuric and nitric acid. Nitrogen was determined by semimicro combustion technique.

Physical Measurements: Electronic spectra were recorded with Hilger Waats UVISPEK spectrophotometer using 1 cm light path. Infrared spectra were recorded by KBr disc technique. Molecular weights were determined by Rast⁶ method. Magnetic moments were obtained as usual⁷. Conductance was measured at 10⁻³M concentration in dimethylformamide (DMF).

Results and Discussion

The procedure adopted by Ablov *et al*³ consists of adding a hot aqueous solution of CuCl₂·2H₂O to a hot methanolic solution of a mixture of the Schiff base and the heterocyclic base, being followed by the addition of sodium acetate. Under such reaction condition a large scale scrambling by the Schiff base and the heterocyclic base for copper(II) is likely. We have fixed the copper(II) as a dipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline complex prior to the reaction with the Schiff base and have thus generated a template about which the mixed chelate formation can take place smoothly. Contrary to Ablov our products are anhydrous.

Conductivity and Molecular weight: All the complexes are non-electrolytes in DMF (Table 2). These values discard alternative isomeric and ionic formulations such as [Cu(*o*-phen)₂][Cu(L)₂] or [Cu(dipy)₂][Cu(L)₂]. The insolubilities of the present chelates in common organic solvents suggest some intermolecular interactions. One possibility is a polymeric⁸ structure in which the Schiff base sulphur occupies an apical site in a distorted octahedral arrangement about the copper atom of another molecule. In fact several isomeric structures will arise due to the bridging possibility of oxygen as well as of sulphur. Their insolubility in benzene, nitrobenzene or bromoform restricted cryoscopic determinations of their molecular weights in these solvents. Solubility in chloroform is also very low, which permits only running the electronic spectra, leaving the extinction coefficient uncertain. However, some determinations have been made in molten comphor (Table 3). Table 3 shows that the values may even vary to the extent of $\pm 20\%$. These data, however, leave no doubt about concentration dependence of the molecular weights.

Magnetic Moments: Our room temperature magnetic data (Table 2) do not reveal any distinctive feature.

Infrared spectra: The IR assignments (Table 4) are based on corresponding assignments in thiosemicarbazide and their complexes^{9,10} as well as on those discussed by us previously¹.

All the Schiff base ligands reveal bands of strong intensity at $\sim 835-840$ cm⁻¹ characteristic of C=S stretching frequency. The infrared spectra of all the free Schiff base ligands have some bands around 3400-3000 cm⁻¹. This region⁹ is characteristic for the NH₂ stretching frequencies in thiosemicarbazide,

NOTES

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF COPPER(II) MIXED CHELATES

LH ₂ (Ia)	Colour	% of Cu		% of N		% of S	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found
		[Cu(o-phen)(L)]					
X = H	dark green	14.5	14.3	16.0	15.9	7.3	7.8
X = 5,6 benzo	shining black	—	—	14.3	13.9	6.5	6.6
X = 5-chloro	shining black	13.5	13.2	14.9	14.7	6.8	6.6
		[Cu(dipy)(L)]					
X = H	shining dark green	15.4	15.2	16.9	16.6	7.7	7.5
X = 5,6 benzo	dark brown	13.7	13.3	15.1	14.6	6.9	7.1
X = 5-chloro	shining black	14.2	14.0	15.7	15.2	7.2	7.5

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND CONDUCTIVITY DATA OF THE MIXED CHELATES

Compounds	LH ₂ (Ia)	$\chi M_{corr} \times 10^6$	T°K	μ_{eff}	Conductivity (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹) in DMF at 25°
[Cu(o-phen)(L)]	X = 5,6 benzo	1204	303	1.71	~1
[Cu(dipy)(L)]	„	1397	303	1.84	~1
[Cu(dipy)(L)]	X = H	1282	303	1.77	~2
[Cu(o-phen)(L)]	X = 5-chloro	1325	303	1.79	~2
[Cu(dipy)(L)]	„	1214	303	1.72	~2

TABLE 3—MOLECULAR WEIGHTS OF THE MIXED CHELATES

Compounds	LH ₂ (Ia)	Wt. of camphor	Wt. of complex	Depression (°C)	Mol.wt. of monomer	Mol.wt. found
[Cu(dipy)(L)]	X = 5,6 benzo	2.0016	0.0931	4	462.5	454
		2.0019	0.1324	4		647
		2.0014	0.2064	4.5		896
		2.0013	0.3029	6		896
		2.0011	0.3028	7		841
		2.0011	0.3028	7.5		785
[Cu(o-phen)(L)]	X = 5,6 benzo	2.0016	0.1056	2.5	486.5	825
		2.0016	0.1056	2		1031
		2.0018	0.2000	2.5		1563
		2.0020	0.2998	3.5		1674

TABLE 4—INFRARED SPECTRAL ASSIGNMENT OF THE LIGANDS AND THE MIXED CHELATES (IN CM⁻¹)

Ligand/complex	dipy/o-phen	$\nu_{C=S}^{10}$	$\nu_S H^{11}$	$\nu_{NH} \& NH_2^{9,10}$
[LH ₂] (X = 5,6 benzo)	—	826 s	no band at 2550–2600	3279 w 3175 w
[LH ₂] (X = H)	—	835 s	„	3509 m 3226 w
[LH ₂] (X = 5, Cl)	—	835 m	„	3279 w 3175 w
[Cu(o-phen)(L)] (X = 5,6 benzo)	735 s 1439 s	—	„	3333 w 3175 w
[Cu(o-phen)(L)] (X = H)	733 s 1433 m	—	„	3311 w 3205 w
[Cu(dipy)(L)] (X = 5,6 benzo)	740 m 1433 m	—	„	3311 w 3175 w
[Cu(dipy)(L)] (X = H)	741 w 1449 m	—	„	3333 w 3175 w
[Cu(dipy)(L)] (X = 5-Cl)	741 m 1427 m	—	„	3279 w 3226 w

[Cu(dipy)Cl₂] have bands at 1440 vs, 1167 s, 730 cm⁻¹ and [Cu(o-phen)Cl₂] shows bands at 1420 s, 1195 wsh, 735 cm⁻¹. However, the bands at 1167 and 1196 cm⁻¹ overlap with other ligand vibrations. s = strong; m = medium; w = weak; sh = shoulder.

which have bands for NH and NH₂ stretching mode¹⁰ at 3370, 3270 and 3190 cm⁻¹. The most notable points is the absence of any S-H band around 2600-2550 cm⁻¹ in any of these ligands. We are

ONO hydrazone Schiff bases and a dipyriddyloxy (or *o*-phenanthroline) (chromophore [Cu N₄O₂] in pyridine 15.6-16.1 kK)¹ the present complexes register a band at higher energy despite their having a sulphur donor.

TABLE 5—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR COPPER(II) MIXED CHELATES

Compounds	State	Colour in solution	Absorption bands in kK	ϵ_{max}
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] (X = H)	Pyridine	green	17.2	215
	Chloroform	green	17.2	*
	Reflectance	dark green	no peak resolved	
[Cu(dipy)(L)] (X = H)	Pyridine	green	17.2	302
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] (X = 5,6 benzo)	Pyridine	dark yellow	18.1	281
	Chloroform	green	17.6	*
[Cu(dipy)(L)] (X = 5,6 benzo)	Pyridine	yellowish green	18.1-17.9	251
[Cu(<i>o</i> -phen)(L)] (X = 5,6 benzo)	Pyridine	green	17.2	212
	Chloroform	yellow	17.5	*
[Cu(dipy)(L)] (X = 5-Cl)	Pyridine	green	17.2-16.9	211

* Molar extinction coefficient can not be determined with certainty because of very poor solubility.

thus convinced that the free ligands have the thioketo structure (Ia) rather than structure (Ib) or (Ic). In the copper(II) mixed chelates the C=S frequencies are absent. The chelates are all non-electrolytes and their IR spectra also do not show any S-H band. Having recourse to our earlier observations¹ on the hydrazone Schiff bases and their chelates we can safely conclude that the thiosemicarbazide Schiff bases are attached to copper(II) in the present mixed chelates in the form (IIa) rather than (IIb) or (IIc). Table 4 also presents some characteristic bands of coordinated dipyriddyloxy or *o*-phenanthroline, which are not present in the free ligands but are found in the mixed chelates as also in [Cu(dipy)Cl₂] and [Cu(*o*-phen)Cl₂].

Electronic spectra: The solid state spectra (e.g. of [Cu(*o*-phen)(L)] (Ia; X = H) are dominated by a strong charge transfer interaction, there being no well resolved peak. The spectra in pyridine and in chloroform (Table 5) show a broad, asymmetric band around ~17-18 kK. The band position in chloroform would be consistent with a six coordinate [CuN₃O₂S] (bridging oxygen) or [CuN₃OS₂] (bridging sulphur) chromophore resulting through polymerisation. In pyridine the band positions are slightly shifted. However, there is a disturbing feature that compared to the copper(II) mixed chelates containing

We believe the inductive effect of the terminal NH₂ group of our ONS Schiff bases scores over that of the phenyl group of the previous ONO Schiff bases giving a higher ligand field effect.

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